

Quantum Fields, Gravity, and Cosmic Structures in Dream-Space

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Abstract

Consciousness experiences forces, gravity, and motions that are restricted to dream-space, and to dream-wake transitions. Study was done to determine the physical models for phenomenology of dream-related forces, gravity, and motions. Consciousness was modeled as frame of reference that observes events in dream and wake spaces. Narratives of forces, gravity, and motions that were observable only in dream-space were preprocessed using natural language algorithms. Machine learning algorithms were used to query documents, perform computational linguistics, and generate knowledge graphs. Median age of 253 subjects was 24 years (50 % inter-quartile range, 21–25). Proportions of themes (95 % CI) were 56 % (51–62) for blackholes, 25 % (20–30) for free fall, 13 % (9–17) for flying, and 6 % (3–8) for teleportation. Dreams occur in dual space of past, present, and future events. Superposition of classical, relativity, and quantum mechanics is observable in dream-space, where Consciousness exists in superposition of physiological and pathological states. The limit of observable reality, therefore, extends from quantum scale to cosmic scale in dream-space. Thus, similar physical laws govern dream and wake spaces.

KEYWORDS consciousness, dreams, gravity, quantum, relativity, wave, nonlocality, blackhole

1. Introduction

Our revels now are ended.

These our actors,

As I foretold you,

were all spirits and

Are melted into air,

And, like the baseless
 fabric of this vision,
 The cloud-capp'd towers,
 the gorgeous palaces,
 The solemn temples,
 the great globe itself,
 Yea, all which it inherit,
 shall dissolve
 And, like this insubstantial
 pageant faded,
 Leave not a rack behind.
 We are such stuff
 As dreams are made on,
 and our little life
 Is rounded with a sleep.

(Williams Shakespeare, *Tempest*, Act
 IV, Scene 1)

Global dynamics of Consciousness spans
 dream-wake cycles (Oluwole, 2020, 2022,
 2025a; Oluwole, 2025b), but observable
 space, time, forces, gravity, and motions
 in dream-space often contradict the real-
 ity of wake-space. Free fall, falling into
 dark holes, flying, space travel, inability
 to move, and instantaneous transit time,

which dominate dream-space, are not ex-
 periences of Consciousness in wake-space
 (Freud, 1900; Griffith et al., 1958; Mag-
 giolini et al., 2007; Nielsen et al., 2003;
 Oluwole, 2019; Yu, 2008). Consciousness,
 therefore, moves with the physical body in
 wake-space, but without it in dream-space.
 While force, gravity, and motion themes
 in dream-space often provoke bizarreness,
 Consciousness has been modeled as ob-
 server frame of reference in dream-wake cy-
 cles (Oluwole, 2020, 2022, 2025a). Ob-
 servable themes in dream and wake spaces
 are, therefore, valid reality. Morphisms of
 past, present, and future events in dream-
 space (Oluwole, 2025b) suggests dual space
 for all reality that Consciousness perceives
 in wake-space. Dualism implies that phe-
 nomenology of space, time, forces, gravity,
 and motions in dreams-space have physical
 basis.

Ontology of Consciousness is dynamic in
 dream-wake cycles (Oluwole, 2022). Ob-
 servable attributes of Consciousness in
 wake-space include cognition, perception,
 language, emotion, and behavior (Oluwole,
 2022), but these exist in superposition with
 entanglement, teleportation, and tunnel-
 ing in dream-space (Oluwole, 2025a; Olu-
 wole, 2025b). Spacetime also exists in su-
 perposition of past, present, and future in
 dream-space (Oluwole, 2025a), while geom-
 etry or morphology of Consciousness can

be in superposition with diverse entities in nature (Oluwole, 2025b). Consciousness is in relativistic motion in dream-space, which has attributes of quantum field, and strong gravity. The weirdness, and strangeness of relativity and quantum mechanics are, therefore, observable in dream-space. Ego dissolution of Consciousness in dream-space (Blanke & Metzinger, 2009; Klatzky, 1998; Noel et al., 2016) implies that its ontology is not fundamental, but built from components. Merging of Consciousness with all matter after ego-dissolution (Lebedev et al., 2015; Milliere, 2017; Nour et al., 2016; Sebastian, 2020; Shanon, 2002) implies that Consciousness interacts with quantum fields. Perception of forces, and gravity themes of Cosmic structures is, therefore, attributable to interactions with gravitational waves during dreams. Study was done to determine the physical models for phenomenology of forces, gravity, and motion in dream-space.

2. Methods

The ontology of Consciousness was modeled to be dynamic in dream-wake cycles. Its state has classical attributes in normal wake-space, but superposition of both classical and quantum states in dream-space. Classical attributes include perception, cognition, language, behaviour, emo-

tion, and metacognition, while quantum attributes include entanglement, teleportation, and tunneling (Kahn, 2019; Oluwole, 2020, 2022).

2.1. Subjects, and Narrative Pre-processing

Subjects were medical students, who provided one to three dream narratives of motion and gravity themes that were exclusive to dreams. The dreams could have been experienced at any time in the past. Motions were local if observable or realizable on Earth's surface, or atmosphere, but non-local if extraterrestrial. Motions were also grouped as Newtonian, or non-Newtonian. Details of forces, gravity, motions, settings, time, entities, and events were provided. Methods of analyses included ontology representations, information science, machine learning queries and summaries, computational linguistics, knowledge graphs, and narrative analysis.

Dream narratives were preprocessed for specific applications. Preprocessing included changing alphabets to lower case, and removal of typographical errors, repeated words, spaces, punctuations, and symbols. Words were changed to their roots like went to go, and running to run. Corpus of dream narratives with local gravity and motion themes, and that with non-local

themes were compared.

2.2. Computational Linguistics, and Artificial Intelligence Queries and Summaries

Keyphrases that were searched for in each corpus included soaring in space, floating, flying, sinking, unable to move, heavy weight, constricting force, and sudden disappearance. Keyphrases were extracted using sgrank algorithm, which was implemented in Textacy module of Python environment. Word clouds were generated using Matplotlib module of Python Programming. Lexical similarity between local, and non-local themes were compared with Jaccard index. Bootstrap statistics was performed to determine 95 % CI for Jaccard similarity.

Machine learning algorithm for document summaries, and queries was implemented in Lmaindex module of Python Programming using Llama3 large language model. Summaries and queries were generated for local, and non-local themes. Queries were designed to retrieve knowledge of forces, gravity, and motions that are exclusive to dreams.

2.3. Entity Extraction, and Knowledge Graphs

Entities in dream narratives were extracted using rule-based entity recognition algorithm, which was implemented in Spacy module of Python Programming. Keyphrases which included soaring in space, falling in space, floating, flying, sinking, unable to move, heavy weight, constricting force, sudden disappearance, and extraterrestrial were combined to themes local, and non-local themes Frequency of themes were calculated with 95 % CI using the Statsmodels module of Python programming.

Each dream narrative was transformed to vector representation with Llama3 large language model. Vector representations were combined to matrix representation. Matrix representation was transformed to affinity matrix of pairwise cosine distances. Affinity matrix was transformed to adjacency matrix by thresholding. Knowledge graph was generated from adjacency matrix using Networkx module of Python Programming. Metrics of the knowledge graph were calculated. Wasserstein distance was used to compare the knowledge graph and Erdos-Renyi random graph. Statistical significance of randomness was determined using Bootstrap statistical method.

Equivalent number of sentences in the cor-

pus of dream narratives were randomly sampled from novels, novelas, and public documents, and bound to corpora. These documents, together with local and non-local themes, were transformed to vector representations with Llama3 large language model. Vector representations were combined to matrix representation. Affinity matrix, and knowledge graphs were generated. Metrics of the document knowledge graph were computed.

2.4. Ethics, and Funding

No funding, grants, or financial support was received from any Organization. Ethical clearance was obtained locally. There was compliance with international guidelines of cognitive research on humans. Informed consent was obtained from subjects, who freely provided information, without financial inducement or coercion. Subjects were assured privacy of personal data provided.

3. Results

There were 253 subjects, 141 (56 %) males, and 112 (44 %) females. Median age (50 % inter-quartile range) was 24 years (21–25). Of 319 themes (95 % CI) 56 % (51–62) were blackholes, 25 % (20–30) were free fall, 13 % (9–17) were flying, and 6 % (3–8) were wormholes, or teleportation. The settings

of dream events (95 % CI) were terrestrial in 83 % (79–88). All avolitional motion themes persisted to immediate wake period.

Five commonest keyphrases in Newtonian narratives were *fly, saw, fall, sky, and night*, but *move, unable, run, like, and try* in non-Newtonian narratives (Figures 1A and 1B). Jaccard index for comparison of Newtonian narratives with non-Newtonian narratives was 0.3 (95 % CI 0.27–0.39). Avolitional motion themes were terminable free fall in terrestrial space, interminable free fall in terrestrial and extraterrestrial spaces, flying in terrestrial or extraterrestrial space, inability to initiate motion, increase or constricting weight, cessation of motion, falling into bottomless pits, no motion in dark places, and instantaneous transit time.

Text summary of Newtonian narratives was *The author has shared several recurring themes and experiences related to their dreams. They have had multiple instances where they felt like they were being chased or pursued by unknown entities, often resulting in them waking up suddenly. In these dreams, they frequently experience superhuman abilities such as defying gravity, flying, swimming, and escaping danger with ease. The author also mentions recurring themes of falling from great heights, feeling a sense of reassurance or relief upon waking, and experiencing vivid and intense*

emotions during these dreams, but for non-Newtonian narratives was *The provided text appears to be a collection of personal experiences and accounts of recurring dreams. The individual describes various scenarios they have experienced while asleep, including feeling trapped or unable to move, being chased, experiencing vivid emotions, and having sensations that blur the lines between reality and fantasy.*

Large language model (LLM) response to the query *are unable to move, darkness, falling into holes attributes of blackholes?* was No for Newtonian corpus, but for non-Newtonian corpus was *darkness and falling into holes do appear in some of the dreams shared, which may be potentially linked to blackhole-related themes. For instance, the dreams involving pits or wells, like the one experienced in 2017, might be related to feelings of being overwhelmed or trapped, which could be reminiscent of a blackhole's powerful gravitational pull. In conclusion, while being unable to move is a common theme across various dream scenarios, darkness and falling into holes may be more specifically linked to potential blackhole-related themes.*

Response to LLM query *is vanishing attribute of wormholes?* was *Wormholes are hypothetical shortcuts through space-time that could potentially connect two dis-*

tant points in space. If we were to interpret "vanishing" as an attribute of wormholes, it would imply that wormholes have the ability to make objects or people disappear from one point and reappear at another. However, this interpretation is not supported by the context information provided. In conclusion, based on the given context information, it seems more likely that "vanishing" refers to a recurring theme in the narrator's dreams rather than an attribute of wormholes. Regarding teleportation, LLM response was *Yes, the experience described appears to be a form of teleportation, as you suddenly found yourself running into a house that appeared while you were being pursued, and then discovered that your brother's house was actually located in Lagos, which you had not previously known. This sudden transformation of location without traversing the physical distance is consistent with the concept of teleportation.*

Semantic network graph of all narratives had 256 nodes with 31,129 connections (Figure 2). Wasserstein distance of knowledge graph from Erdos-Renyi random graph was 230 (95 % CI 229–231). Metrics were 1.0 for highest degree centrality, 0.95 for density, 2.0 for diameter, 2.0 for radius, and 0.96 for average clustering coefficient. There were two communities in the semantic graph using Louvain algorithm.

Documents were Newtonian corpus, non-Newtonian corpus, and corpora of Adventures of Huckleberry, Adventures of Sherlock Holmes, Brother Karamazov, Christmas Carol, News Editorial, Great Expectations, Gulliver Travels, Heart of Darkness, Importance of Been Earnest, Letter Montaigne, Little Women, News, Oliver Twist, Sense and Sensibility, State of the Union Address, Tale of Two Cities, The Awakening, The Jungle, The Republic, Treasure Island, Ulysses, War of Worlds, and Wizzard of Oz.

Document semantic network graph was directed, and unconnected with 25 nodes and 18 edges (Figure 3). Its subgraph of 10 nodes were Christmas Carol, News Editorial, Great Expectations, Gulliver Travels, Importance of Been Earnest, Letter Montaigne, The Jungle, War of Worlds, Newtonian corpus, and non-Newtonian corpus. There was no connectivity between Newtonian corpus and non-Newtonian corpus, but News Editorial and Gulliver Travels were connected to Newtonian narratives and non-Newtonian narratives, while Great Expectations was connected to Newtonian narratives alone, and The Jungle to non-Newtonian narratives alone.

3.1. Narratives Of Motion and Gravity Themes in Dreams

Dream narratives which illustrates themes of free fall, flying, blackhole wormholes, dream-wake transitions are shown:

Terminable Free Falls

- (1) *"I was falling from the sky and there was no one to hold me, I thought I was going to hit the ground and die, but I woke up before hitting the ground due to fear"*
- (2) *"I was in an unknown city with tall buildings and I just walked off one of the building and I had the feeling of falling through the sky before I woke up spontaneously with jerking movements in one of my legs and palpitations "*
- (3) *"I was falling off a swing"*
- (4) *"This was 2 years back, I was on the balcony of my parents home. I was standing on the edge of the fence looking downwards, then I felt a sudden force push me. the distance looked very far as I fell, but I soon woke up suddenly and felt like I jumped on the bed in a split second. I was breathing heavily and was very scared. I have not thought about it recently"*

Interminable Free Falls

- (5) *"Around 2016, I dreamt I fell from a staircase and kept falling. I woke up screaming for help then my mum came to my room and asked what happened. She kept shaking me till I could finally move"*
- (6) *"I was being harassed, threatened by an unknown person, then I got struggled to get loose and started running. As I ran, I was aware that the person might be chasing me. I eventually got to a cliff of sorts, maybe the roof of a building and jumped. Though it felt as though I was falling space even though I realized it was not such a far distance, it still felt as though I was falling for ages, maybe my body was weightless and I did not have control over it. (it was wired)"*
- (7) *"falling from a bridge yet could not fall inside the sea"*
- (8) *"Unknown year some where in childhood. I would often have dreams of falling down from a high cliff. This again, like many of any dreams, it was the night. It was never a case of someone pushing me down, it was always as though I just stepped down from the high place and the fall was always like I was falling into bottomless pit, I would mostly up mid-fall and it was always preceded by breathlessness, like I was struggling to catch my breath for*
- so long a time while falling when I did then I would up gasping for air. I believed this happened about 3 or 4 times through childhood. "*
- (9) *"I was standing at the edge of a very tall building or cliff firstly unable to move and all of a sudden, I could feel myself falling and falling to the ground or to the bottom and sinking but all I could see was darkness everywhere and then I up, scare, anxious and sweaty. This has happened on several occasions at night. I don't usually recall what leads to that event. It could be a series of meaningless events but the memorable /part of one dream is usually me falling from somewhere and then I up. There has only been one of me I can't recall that I woke up crying"*
- (10) *"I was in a dark room/box. I was trying to find out where to pass or what to see until the ground opened in front of me. I fell into a hole beneath. Falling like that felt for so long and I jerked from sleep afterwards "*
- (11) *"Between 2017-2020 about 5 times in a year. I had dreamt at different times, alight on the edge of a cliff in an unknown planet. Feels like Australia. Then a strong wind came which indged me to fall off the cliff. I felt ?Frozen? while falling. I was an endless fall and looked like I will never hit the ground. I*

woke up abruptly and I was motionless"

Flying in Terrestrial Space

(12) *"Jumping in between trees and flying through the sky "*

(13) *"flying with friends or being chased by dangerous faceless beings and vanishing when almost caught"*

(14) *"About 26yrs ago,when I had a dream that I was being followed by some group of men their identity are unknown to be. In the dream they have an intention of fighting me. Suddenly, I saw myself in the sky flying, they tried flying up too but I kept kicking them on the head. Then I woke up."*

(15) *"Flying and helping people to facilitate their need. It involves even flying above high rise buildings and seeing very far distance to help people in danger"*

(16) *"I was a flying super heroine. A kind of female superman. I was basically helping out during the extreme covid outbreak in China"*

Flying in Extraterrestrial Space

(17) *" Early 2021, I dreamt about myself floating or flying not sure which out of my house. It felt like I was being shot up such that I was seeing the ground more and more distant. It started with the roof of my house then seeing it almost as a dot, then seeing clouds, then I*

was out of planet earth. I could see the planet slowly revolving with the bluish part, greenish part and cloudy parts after which I woke up"

(18) *"I was soaring in extraterrestrial space including vanishing from space at the verge of danger"*

Strong Gravity Themes

(19) *"I dreamed that two old men were trying to lift a carton box on one of their head. Looking at the box it did not seem heavy because it was actually full of clothes but it also surprised me that they really struggled to lift it up. As I kept on watching they tried and tried but could not, at some point they will almost lift it up but then just as soon as the lift it up the become very tired and drop it down. I then offered to help them you know that feeling when you think something is light then you try lifting it only to see that it is rather drawing you to the ground. I struggled to lift it up. I really strained and my vertebral column almost broke but then I finally lifted put it on my head only for the contents to fall out. At this point, I was pissed off and tired so I decided to ignore them drop the box and continues with my activities. At this point I woke up"*

(20) *"I was being chased by some people*

- and I noticed I was running so fast in my mind but in actual sense, I was running 10 times slower. As they were about to catch me I woke up "
- (21) " I know when I try to scream out for help in my dreams, I can never make out any words. I don't run fast enough in my dreams. When some is chasing me. Usually in a desert with blood red skies, when I fall I normally up"
- (22) "In the dream, I remember feeling very anxious and afraid although the reason was not clear. I tried running but I just could not run fast enough in the dream so I felt frustrated. The dream seemed to last a few minutes" '
- (23) "trying to run but having some problem running forward"
- (24) "unable to move in the dream even though I wanted "
- (25) "I often feel being tied down and unable to escape. I often realize it happens when my legs are closed in the physical"
- (26) "In 2008, i found it extremely hard to wake from this dream. I recall feeling the sun on my face that morning, trying to get up but being unable to. It was so frightening that I tried screaming for help but couldn't do that either. I felt trapped in my body"
- (27) "the dream included being dragged down,unable to move then suddenly there was a glimpse of hope as a motion in very bright place which pulled me out. I woke up immediately after the dream"
- (28) "In 2012, I had another dream at night where I was at the bottom of the sea. Everywhere was dark and I could not move either because of terror or of some immobilizing force. Then I began to see red eyes all around me and tentacles entangling me. I thought of the dream continually. I don't think this dream expressed any significant worries at that time except maybe fear of the dark spiritual powers."
- '
- (29) Sometime in 2018, I was in a dream at night, I can't really recall how and where what happened because the whole place was dark in that dream, but all I know was that I was lying down on bed in that dream, on attempt to stand up and join other outside, it was as if smoothing, or a force pinned me to the bed, I couldn't stand, to breath was an issue, even to call for help was not possible because it was as if I lost my voice on that dream, I was only shouting blood of Jesus inside my mind but I couldn't ever hear myself. That lasted for a while and I was struggling with that unseen force until I opened my eye to discover that it was all a dream. All through that night, I kept vigil, even to

close my eyes was an issues because I was very scared of the occurrence in the previous dream and never want a repeat"

- (30) *i was in a very dark environment without light. all effort to get out of there was abortive. i started shouting for help. suddenly i saw a very intense light even too bright for me to see. after a while i passed into another region of green plantation filled with numerous fruits. This dream is from a previous study (Oluwole, 2020).*

Interminable Transits

These dreams were provided as supplementary data from previous studies (Oluwole, 2020, 2022)

- (31) *"i was climbing the stairs in the university college hospital to go and see a friend in the Ward. But all of a sudden i noticed a weird noise from behind. afterwards i started running. i was just climbing the stairs as if it was endless*
- (32) *" I was in University of Ibadan Hall of Residence. I was looking for someone in a particular room. The place was hell of bends and curves and could not remember when University of Ibadan Hall of Residence became like that. I got to one room that looked like it but the person I met said that it was not the room. I kept on trying ...*

Wormhole or Teleportation Themes In Dreams

- (33) *"I was beside a river with some of my family relation/friends and all of a sudden i saw myself in the sky and my relations were still on land"*
- (34) *"I have been dreaming of travelling to Canada. I saw all my siblings in Canada and i could not recognize most of them again. Then suddenly I discovered myself in another country which I could not remember the country"*
- (35) *"i was being pursued by a heard of cattle. i could not explain why i was being pursued. all of a sudden i ran into a house that appeared when i was running. when i got in my brother was inside. he was repairing his car. when i told him i was being pursued, we came outside, but there were no cattle. what we saw was an expressway that led to lagos. before we could step out i noticed that my brother's house was now in lagos. all of a sudden a big truck now drove towards the house as if it wants to bring the house down. but before it hit the house"*
- (36) *"i was driving a 504 wagon and with me were three of my friends. i think we were travelling to lagos for an event. but, along the way we appeared in benin. we decided to stop over and eat. but, as we parked, a car came from nowhere*

and started honking. the honking was getting louder. before i could turn to see the driver, i ended up waking to put off my alarm"

(37) *At a stage I was in University College Hospital with colleagues. Then it shifted to University of Ibadan, and then to my Secondary School*

Wormhole or Teleportation from Dreams to Wake-Space

(38) *"I was at the verge of being attacked and I woke up suddenly"*

(39) *"This was 2 years back, i was on the balcony of my parents home. I was standing on the edge of the fence looking downwards, then I felt a sudden force push me. the distance looked very far as i fell, but i soon woke up suddenly and felt like i jumped on the bed in a split second. I was breathing heavily and was very scared. i have not thought about it recently "*

(40) *"I had a dream 3 nights ago that I was being chased by my dad with stones and I kept running hoping he was going to be tired and stop chasing me but that didn't happen so I had to jump from a storey building because I knew there was no way he was jumping after me. I felt the landing on my bed and i woke up"*

(41) *"I had a dream about 6 years ago. There is a bridge we have to cross*

when going to church. In this dream I was walking with my family to church and on getting to this bridge, I kind of slipped and fell through the rail by the side. I woke up immediately and still had this feeling like I was falling when I woke up. It took a while for me to calm down"

(42) *"The dream occurred in the year 2015.*

Setting was behind school hostel, there were only three characters of whom were my classmates. In the dream, we were drowning in a water puddle behind the hostel. On attempt for me to swim away, I felt a force pulling me down. I woke up with a jerking motion"

(43) *"I recall being unable to move sometimes after waking, with associated difficulty breathing and feeling of being in a vacuum - no air or sound"*

(44) *"unable to move after waking up but I am aware of my surrounding"*

(45) *"I was a but unable to move my body for a few seconds even though I could blink my eyes"*

4. Discussion

Distribution of narratives indicates that non-Newtonian forces, gravity, and motions predominant in dream-space. The settings of these motion themes are, however, significantly terrestrial. Free fall in dream-space

is Newtonian when it terminates on the surface of the Earth, but non-Newtonian free fall is interminable, terminates by sinking into the ground, or with Consciousness surrounded by darkness. Flying in Earth's atmosphere, or in space is Newtonian if it is observable in wake-space or mimics motions of projectiles into space. Forces that restrict initiation of motion, or stop all motions in dark places are non-Newtonian. Discontinuous motion that mimics teleportation of quantum mechanics, or wormholes of general relativity mechanics is non-Newtonian. Thus, attributes of classical, general relativity, and quantum mechanics are observable in dream-space of subjects.

Machine learning text summaries indicate that corpora of Newtonian and non-Newtonian narratives encode knowledge of mechanics, and dynamics. Text summary of non-Newtonian narratives encodes knowledge of general relativity and quantum mechanics. Vocabulary representation of experience encodes spatial and temporal attributes of events, occurrence, emotions, and knowledge. Vocabulary of dream narratives is not restrictive, but is comparable to diverse genre of documents (Oluwole, 2020, 2022). *Fly, saw, fall, sky, and night* which are the commonest keyphrases in Newtonian narrative indicate phenomenology that is different from *move, unable, run, like, and try* for non-Newtonian nar-

ratives (Figure 1). Statistical difference in Jaccard similarity, therefore, indicates that phenomenology of non-Newtonian narratives is distinct. Thus, phenomenology of forces, gravity, and motions in dream-space is not homogeneous.

Semantic representation of experience extracts meanings, entities, concepts, and ontologies from narratives. Semantics of dream narratives clustered with restricted genre of documents, although the vocabulary was comparable to diverse genre of documents (Oluwole, 2020). Semantic network graphs reveal documents with similar semantics or encoded knowledge. Bootstrap statistics indicate that semantic network graph of subjects' narratives is not random. Metrics of the network graph indicate that encoded knowledge in the narratives is connected, undirected, and dense. Absence of isolated nodes in the network indicates that subjects have similar phenomenal experiences of forces, gravity, and motions that are exclusive to dreams (Figure 2). Two communities in the graph agrees with partitioning of narratives in Newtonian, and non-Newtonian. Dream narratives of forces, gravity, and motion in recurrent dreams of diverse culture imply consensus (Griffith et al., 1958; Nielsen, 1993; Oluwole, 2019; Schredl et al., 2004; Yu, 2008). Thus, Consciousness experiences similar reality of forces, gravity, and mo-

tions that are restricted to dream-space.

Semantic network graph of Newtonian and non-Newtonian narratives, novels, novels, and public documents is also not random, but is, however, directed, and unconnected (Figure 3). The network graph, therefore, has isolated documents which encode unshared knowledge. Of 25 document nodes the connected subgraph has 10 nodes, which include Christmas Carol, News Editorial, Great Expectations, Gulliver Travels, Importance of Been Earnest, Letter Montaigne, The Jungle, War of Worlds, Newtonian corpus, and non-Newtonian corpus (Figure 3). In the subgraph, Newtonian and non-Newtonian narratives are connected to News Editorial, and Gulliver Travels. Newtonian corpus is connected to Great Expectations, while non-Newtonian corpus is connected to The Jungle. Newtonian corpus and non-Newtonian corpus are, however, not connected, which indicates differences in encoded knowledge. Thus, phenomenology of Newtonian and non-Newtonian mechanics in dream-space is distinct, but not disconnected from reality encoded in other human documents.

Objective realism asserts that ontology exists independent of observers. While perception is subjective (Ramachandran & Hirstein, 1997), phenomenology is established if there is perceptual consensus

(Moran, 2024; White, 1947). Objective reality, therefore, is free of notions and beliefs of observers, but is knowable, and governed by physical laws. Perceptual consensus of observable space, time, forces, gravity, and motions in dream-space of subjects, and of diverse cultures (Griffith et al., 1958; Nielsen et al., 2003; Oluwole, 2019; Yu, 2008) imply objective reality. Findings, therefore, indicate that vocabulary, and encoded information in narratives and semantic network graphs established perceptual consensus of subjects. Thus, reality in dream-space compliments experiences of wake-space.

4.1. Content Analysis of Dream Narratives

Free fall in gravity fields is the second commonest theme in dream-space of subjects. In Earth's gravity field, free fall terminates on the surface of the Earth, where contact force prevents entities from sinking. Free fall is overrepresented in recurrent dreams than common motion themes like walking, or running (Oluwole, 2019). It is recurrent in the dreams of 83 % Americans (Griffith et al., 1958), 74 % Japanese (Griffith et al., 1958) and Canadians (Nielsen et al., 2003), 87 % Chinese (Yu, 2008), and 51 % Nigerians (Oluwole, 2019). Free fall in Dreams 1–4 terminates before reaching the

surface of the Earth, on the surface of the Earth, or on sinking to upper surface of the Earth. Additional features in Dreams 1–4 are surrounding darkness during fall, considerable time of the fall compared with short distance to the surface of the Earth, and sudden awakening with jerking of the body, labored breathing, sweating, or crying. Dreams 5–10, however, illustrate interminable free fall in terrestrial space, into a hole which opened spontaneously in the ground in Dream 10, but in extraterrestrial space in Dream 11. Free fall is from staircases, roofs of buildings, cliffs, and bridge in Dreams 5–9. Free fall from a cliff in extraterrestrial space of an unknown Planet is shown in Dream 11. Subjects described free fall as endless motion, falling for ages, or falling into bottomless pit. Additional features are surrounding darkness, weightlessness, sudden awakening, and anxiety. Thus, free fall in dreams may be Newtonian, or non-Newtonian.

4.2. Flying Themes

Flying is the third-commonest avolitional motion theme in dream-space of subjects. Flying, being in extraterrestrial spaces, and seeing angels, aliens, or UFO are overrepresented in recurrent dreams compared with observable motions of wake-space (Oluwole, 2019). Flying is recurrent in the dreams of

34 % Americans (Griffith et al., 1958), 46 % Japanese (Griffith et al., 1958), 48 % Canadians (Nielsen et al., 2003), 64 % Germans (Schredl et al., 2004), 74 % Chinese (Yu, 2008), and 42 % Nigerians (Oluwole, 2019). Dreams 12–16 indicate flying in terrestrial space, which includes scenes of trees, buildings, and upper regions of the atmosphere. Additional features include flying to escape being chased by humans, faceless beings, or for peaceful purposes like helping Covid-19 victims. Motion in extraterrestrial space is recurrent in dreams of 12 % Canadians, 29 % Chinese, and 23 % Nigerians. Seeing extraterrestrials is recurrent in dreams of 10 % Canadians (Nielsen et al., 2003), 26 % Chinese (Yu, 2008), 7 % Germans (Schredl et al., 2004), and 22 % Nigerians. UFOs are recurrent in dreams of 8 % Canadians (Nielsen et al., 2003), but 16 % Nigerians (Oluwole, 2010). Flying in extraterrestrial space is shown in Dreams 17 and 18. In Dream 17, Consciousness is slowly ejected into extraterrestrial space, from where the Earth is observed to be rotating. In Dream 18, however, Consciousness is flying in extraterrestrial space and vanishing from danger. Thus, phenomenology of antigravity motions is observable in dream-space.

4.3. Extraterrestrial Motion Themes

Strong gravity theme that mimic interiors of blackholes is the commonest avolitional motions in dream-space of subjects. While inertia resists volitional motion in wake-space, its extreme is recurrent in the dreams of 30 % Americans (Griffith et al., 1958), 21 % Japanese (Griffith et al., 1958) and Canadians (Nielsen et al., 2003), 35 % Germans (Schredl et al., 2004), and 51 % Nigerians (Oluwole, 2019). Consciousness in Dreams 19–30 perceives inability to move, being tied down, and compressed with force or heavy weight. Dream 19 shows that two men could not lift a light box filled with clothes. Attempt by Consciousness to assist the men almost broke the vertebra. Consciousness is chased in Dreams 20 and 21, but is unable to achieve intended speed to escape. There is fear for no reason in Dream 22, but running is slow, while in Dreams 23–26 Consciousness is unable to run, tied down, or could not escape. Motion is resisted or impossible in dark places in Dreams 27–30. Consciousness is dragged down to dark place where no motion is possible in Dream 27, but pulled up to light, where motion is restored. Consciousness could not move in dark place at the bottom of the sea in Dream 28, but in undefined place in Dream 29. Inability to move in

dark place in Dream 30 is relieved when intense bright light shone. Thus, forces, and gravity that are consistent with attributes of blackholes dominate the dream-space of subjects.

4.4. Infinite, and Instantaneous Transit Times

Transit times between locations on Earth are predictable because distances are not dynamic. In dreams, however, transit times may increase considerably, or become instantaneous (Oluwole, 2020, 2022). Unpredictable transit times are comparable to dream themes of prolonged duration of events, or inability to complete tasks. Occurrences of inability to complete tasks or trying again and again to do something were 71 % in Americans (Griffith et al., 1958), 87 % in Japanese (Griffith et al., 1958), 54 % in Canadians (Nielsen et al., 2003), 30 % in Germans (Schredl et al., 2004), and 48 % in Nigerians. Dreams of being late, or missing events are recurrent in dreams (Griffith et al., 1958; Nielsen et al., 2003; Oluwole, 2019; Schredl et al., 2004; Yu, 2008). Dreams 31–32 indicate interminable transit times between locations that are minimally separated. The flight of stairs deformed and stretched, such that time to climb is infinite in Dream 31. A Hall of Residence deforms to bends and curves

in Dream 32 such that desired room is not located after much effort. Dreams 33–37, however, indicate instantaneous transit between vastly separated locations. Thus, metrics of dream-space are non-Euclidean.

4.5. Teleportation, and Events of Dream-Wake Transition

Continuity, symmetry, or conservation laws define motions in wake-space, but teleportation occurs in dream-space when destinations appear suddenly. Phenomenology of teleportation is similar to wormholes, which are spacetime bridges between vastly separated locations in the Cosmos. In Dream 38 Consciousness teleports to awakening following violent event. Free fall in Dreams 39–40 ends with violent landing of Consciousness on the bed. Perception of free fall from a Bridge persists on awakening in Dream 41. Drowning in Dream 42 ends with jerking on awakening. Sleep paralysis describes phenomenology of heavy weight, constricting force, and inability to move on awakening from dreams (Cheyne, 2005; Oluwole, 2010; Paradis & Friedman, 2005). Sleep paralysis is experienced in Dreams 43–45, where there is inability to move and perception of vacuum, lack of air, and sound. Persistence of dream events to awakening is frequently accompanied by autonomic response, and emotions. These ex-

periences in dreams are, therefore, not fantasies since daydream (Freud, 1908; Singer, 2007; Starker, 1974), fantasy (Freud, 1908), or mind-wandering (McMillan et al., 2013) do not generate skeletal motion. Thus, phenomenology in dream-wake interface is distinct.

4.6. Theories of Gravity, and Observables of Dream-Space

Gravity in dream-space is attributed to encoded memories of free fall from being tossed in the air in childhood (Freud, 1900), but this experience is not universal. Freudian dream theory, however, would not account for free fall into dark holes, perception of strong forces, unable to move, and not reaching destination, which are not experiences of wake-space. Sensors of gravity in wake-space include proprioceptors of joint position, neck movement, and vestibular receptors of head orientation (Gallagher et al., 2021; Proske, 2005; Proske & Gandevia, 2012; Sheets-Johnstone, 2010). Earth’s gravity field (Gaugne Gouranton et al., 2025) stimulates vestibular cortex (Delle Monache et al., 2021), and neuronal networks (Striebel et al., 2023) in vivo and in vitro (Kohn & Ritzmann, 2018a, 2018b). Microgravity, and hypergravity also stimulate neuronal cells (Gontier et al., 2024). While touch (Nielsen, 1993), pain (Nielsen,

1993), sound (Burton et al., 1988), and ongoing events (Bloxham & Durrant, 2014) are perceived in dreams, Earth's gravity is, however, not (Fuller et al., 2007; Peever & Fuller, 2017; Schenck et al., 1993). Thus, gravity in dream-space is not attributable to Earth's gravity field.

Gravity is one of four fundamental interactions in nature that is generated by masses, energy, or EMF. Gravity, therefore, is expected attribute of brain EMF. In Newtonian mechanics, gravity is force of attraction in the potential field of masses. In general relativity mechanics (Bambi, 2018; Luminet, 1998; Wald, 2010), however, it is the curvature of spacetime manifold by masses, energy, or EMF. Since quantum gravity is present in systems that have attributes of both quantum fields and very strong gravity fields, Dreams 33-40 indicate quantum gravity. Dreams 33-37 indicate teleportation within dreams, while Dreams 38-40 indicate teleportation to wake-space. Thus, encoded quantum information in dream-space includes gravity.

Perception of strong forces, extreme gravity fields, and avolitional motion themes are commonest in REM sleep. Configuration of brain EMF during REM sleep is similar to observables of cognitive tasks in wake-space (Simor et al., 2021). Gamma oscillations in brain electrical field couple

to cognitive tasks in wake space (Gross et al., 2007; Steinmann et al., 2014; Tallon-Baudry & Bertrand, 1999), and in dream-space (Acosta-Urquidi, n.d.; Pirazzini & Ursino, 2024). Ponto-geniculo-occipital waves (PGO waves), which originates in the pons and stimulates the visual neocortex, precedes changes in visual cortex during REM sleep (Gao et al., 2023). PGO waves, therefore, is attributable to perception of gravity information through pontine neuronal networks during sleep. Newtonian gravity field is also modeled as gravitoelectric field, while gravity of rotating, or spinning Cosmic structures like neutron stars, and blackholes generate gravito-electromagnetism (GEM) which is perceived on Earth analogous to EMF. Thus, Cosmic structures and extraterrestrial gravity are perceived through interactions Consciousness in dream-space.

The state space of Consciousness spans dream-wake cycles. States of Consciousness in wake-space includes physiological state, and pathological states like psychedelic, psychoses, intoxication, substance abuse, and neuropathological syndromes. Observables of dream-space, however, include physiological and all pathological states of Consciousness. Morphisms of past, present, and future events to dreams, therefore, imply dual space. Superposition of quantum, classical, and relativity mechanics,

therefore, form the basis of the dual space. The complex manifold of the dual space, therefore, permits motions of Consciousness to the past, present, and future. Transition from the dual space to the classical wake-space is, therefore, modeled with De Broglie-Bohm quantum decoherence. Transition of Consciousness to wake-space, however, is not always smooth decoherence, but includes hypnic jerks, sleep paralysis, and lucid dreams. These observables indicate that mixed boundary layer is present between dream and wake spaces. Mixing of distinct topological spaces in boundary layer theory generate turbulence when velocity gradient is steep. Hypnic jerks in Dreams 38–42, which are preceded by violent events, indicate turbulent flow. While hypnic jerks last briefly, however, sleep paralysis in Dreams 43–45, prevented full awakening. Sleep paralysis, therefore, is severe turbulence. Although lucid dream also have attributes of both dream and wake spaces it typically transits to awakening without turbulence. Jerk dynamics of boundary layer theory, therefore, models hypnic jerks. It also models sleep paralysis, but unlike hypnic jerk smooth transition to wake-space is impossible. Lucid dreams, however, transition to wake-space with turbulence. Thus, the limits of observable reality expand to quantum and Cosmic scales in dream-space.

Cartesian dualism asserts that Consciousness is not matter. Matter, however, is composed of fermions, and bosons. Fermions include electrons, neutrinos, protons, and neutrons, while bosons include photons, gluons, and mesons. Entities that move with the speed of light include photons, gluons, and gravity waves. Consciousness, therefore, has attributes of bosons since it moves close to the speed of light in dream-space. It has, also attributes of energy, and momentum. Ego-dissolution of Consciousness supports composite ontology of Consciousness, while equivalence of energy and mass supports merging of Consciousness with matter. Consciousness, therefore, has attributes of matter. Thus, ontology of Consciousness is material, and physical.

5. Conclusion

The rabbit-hole went
straight on like a tunnel
for some way, and then dipped
suddenly down, so suddenly that
Alice had not a moment to think
about stopping herself before
she found herself falling down
a very deep well. Either the

well was very deep, or she fell

very slowly ...

(Alice in Wonderland)

Transformations of Consciousness, space, time, and events in dream-space provide more details of reality than observable in wake-space. Superposition of quantum fields, and strong gravity fields in dream-space indicates quantum gravity. Phenomenology of terminable free fall, ejection of Consciousness to space, and space travels in dream-space are attributes of classical mechanics. Interminable free falls, falling into dark holes, and cessation of motion in dark places in dream-space are attributes of general relativity mechanics, while instantaneous transit is attribute of both general relativity and quantum mechanics. Observable motion themes in dream-space, therefore, have mimics in nature. Thus, forces, gravity, and motions in dream-space can be modeled from first principles of physics.

Morphisms indicate that dream-space is dual space of past, present and future events. There is also dual form of Consciousness in dream-space, where it exists in superposition of all known physiological and pathological states. Observable themes of quantum, classical and relativity mechanic are also in superposition in dream-space. There is, therefore, quantum decoherence of Consciousness on awak-

ening. Hypnic jerks, and sleep paralysis on awakening indicate presence of mixed boundary layer between dream and wake spaces. Lucid dreams also have attributes of mixed boundary layer. Thus, dream-space expands the limits of observable reality to quantum and cosmic scales.

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Figure 1: Commonest Keyphrases

Phenomenology in Newtonian Dream Narratives are modeled with Newtonian Physics, while Non-Newtonian Dream Narratives are modeled with Special, General, and Quantum Physics

Figure 2: Narrative Semantic Network Graph

Nodes of the Network Graph are vectors of each Narrative, while edges are connectivities

Figure 3: Document Semantic Network Graph

News Editorial (4) is connected to Newtonian narratives' corpus (23) and non-Newtonian narratives' corpus (24); Gulliver Travels (6) and Great Expectations (5) are connected to Newtonian corpus (23); The Jungle (17) is connected to non-Newtonian corpus (24); Newtonian corpus (23) and non-Newtonian corpus are not connected; Other nodes are Brother Karamazov (2), Christmas Carol (3), Heart of Darkness (7), Importance of Been Earnest (8), Letter Montaigne (9), Little Women (10), News (11), Oliver Twist (12), Sense and Sensibility (13), State of The Union Addresses (14), Tale of Two Cities (15), The Republic (18), Treasure Island (19), Ulysses (20), War of Worlds (21), and Wizzard of Oz (22)